

Walking through 2700 years of history of Tell Nebi Yunus, Mosul, Iraq in a Virtual Reality
application: A new way to present a heritage site's cultural dynamics

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On 24th of July 2014, the so-called Islamic State of Iraq and the Levant (ISIL) blew up the centuries-old Islamic Nebi Yunus Mausoleum in Mosul, Iraq^{1,2}, which was the presumed burial site of the Biblical and Qur'anic prophet Jonah (*Nebi Yunus*, in Arabic) and which stood on one of the two mounds (*tell*, in Arabic) of the Late Assyrian capital of Nineveh. The city then not only lost one of its religious landmarks and pilgrimage sites, but also an important part of its rich cultural heritage, which, on two levels, included Assyrian, Jewish, Christian, and Islamic elements:

1. The loss of the mausoleum was dire given that, to that date, only one comprehensive scientific study of the building had been conducted, and its shape and dimensions had only been recorded vaguely³. In addition, the possibility to investigate on site the hypothesis, that the Islamic place of worship was originally the church of a *Church of the East* monastery from Late Antiquity⁴⁻⁶, was eliminated. The hypothesis itself is based on observations made by various modern period travellers to Mosul⁷⁻¹⁰, who noticed several architectural characteristics which were unusual for an Islamic mausoleum. Furthermore, Islamic scholars before the 14th century AD did not mention a “tomb of Jonah”¹¹, and wrote more generally about the “Hill of Repentance”^{12,13} or the “place where Jonah stood”¹⁴, which are references to the Biblical story of the prophet who was sent to Nineveh by his god to make its inhabitants repent¹⁵. In 1965, French historian Fiey then combined the various historical accounts and claimed that a 14th century AD discovery of a well-preserved corpse of a 7th-century-AD *Church of the East* patriarch laid to rest in the monastery led to a case of mistaken identity of the patriarch as Jonah. This event was immediately followed by the conversion of the Christian building into an Islamic mausoleum. The fact that “Nineveh” is not mentioned in the Qur'an leads to the question of how early Muslims could have associated a mound near Mosul with Jonah, if it were not for an Early Christian tradition¹⁶. This corroborates the hypothesis and indicates a case of cultural dynamics¹⁷.

2. After the liberation of Mosul in 2017, a large network of tunnels under the mausoleum ruin was discovered by the Iraqi Army, in which Late Assyrian works of art, like large human-headed winged bulls and bas-reliefs, came to light^{18,19}. The observations confirmed what modern era travellers, assyriologists and archaeologists had been assuming since 1820 AD^{9,20-23}: The mausoleum, or monastery, was partially built on a Late Assyrian palace erected by the two 7th century BC kings Sennacherib and Esarhaddon^{24,25}, which must have been destroyed during the Fall of Nineveh in 612 BC²⁶. The tunnels themselves were dug by ISIL between 2014 and 2016 to loot the buried palace and to presumably sell retrieved Late Assyrian artefacts on the black market to finance its war machine²⁷. During this organised crime, the ancient mud brick walls were irreparably damaged.

In this situation, the two questions arose a) how the last 2700 years of Tell Nebi Yunus could be recovered, and b) how this long history of cultural dynamics could be retold and made accessible to modern audiences?

The presentation will give insights into how a georeferenced 3D model of Tell Nebi Yunus was the initial step in answering the first question: SfM-photogrammetric data of the mound's surface and of the looters' tunnels were captured during a project by Heidelberg University from 2018 to 2019²⁸, and were then processed and used, from 2020 to 2025 in a cotutelle PhD project at Heidelberg University and the University of Luxembourg, as a base to virtually 3D reconstruct the different ancient buildings in the open-source 3D modelling software Blender with the Blender GIS addon. In this virtual 3D recovery process realised by isolating either surviving or visible architectural features of both the mausoleum and the palace in the point clouds and by producing Digital Elevation Models, the above-mentioned historical accounts as well as cadastral maps and Royal Air Force aerial reconnaissance photographs taken in the 1920s of Nineveh were of substantial importance too. The resulting 3D models allowed to rethink the cultural heritage site's at least 2700-year-old biography and, thus, to create a 4D model²⁹ of Tell Nebi Yunus with its various construction phases.

Regarding the second question, the presentation will include an Unreal Engine-based Virtual Reality (VR) tour through the aforementioned different building phases. Starting with the chaotic 2018 situation on Tell Nebi Yunus with the looters' tunnels and the destroyed mausoleum, two virtual walks, one below ground and one above ground, try to make sense of what archaeological and art historical phases had been impacted by the 2014 controlled ISIL demolition: Literally jumping a) from 2018 to the distant past, and moving forward in time, the Late Assyrian palace can be explored at the period of king Sennacherib in the 7th century BC, then as a hypothetical ruin at the era of the Greek mercenary Xenophon around 400 BC³⁰; travelling b) from the recent past to 1922, and moving backward in time, the Islamic mausoleum can be investigated at the time of the final days of the Ottoman Empire until the epoch of the 14th-century-AD conversion of the hypothetical *Church of the East* monastery is reached. During the latter, photographs, drawings, and excerpts from historical accounts placed at specific points in the various virtual 3D reconstructions add a human dimension to the VR tour to retell the dynamic history of Tell Nebi Yunus.

In this perspective, experiencing the various construction phases of Tell Nebi Yunus in a 3D environment can open a new way to reinterpret historical accounts from Antiquity and the Middle Ages. In addition, digital technologies combined with historical material can potentially recover a history of cultural dynamics, which ISIL sought to eradicate.

Acknowledgments: Parts of the work described in this contribution were supported by *Fritz Thyssen Stiftung* (2018 – 2019), the *Ministerium für Wissenschaft, Forschung und Kunst Baden-Württemberg* (2019 – 2020), and the *Institute for Advanced Studies Luxembourg* (2022 – 2025).

Bibliography

1. Nicks, D. Islamist Militants Raze Ancient Shrine in Mosul. *TIME* <https://time.com/3033678/iraq-isis-jonah-tomb-mosul/> (2014).
2. Peralta, E. Video Shows Islamic State Blowing Up Iraq's Tomb Of Jonah. *NPR* (2014).
3. Al-Diwahji, S. *Mosques of Mosul in Different Eras*. (Arab Encyclopedia House, Beirut, 2014).
4. Fiey, J. M. *Assyrie Chrétienne. Contribution à l'Étude de l'Histoire et de la Géographie Ecclésiastiques et Monastiques du Nord de l'Iraq. Volume II*. vol. 2 (Imprimerie Catholique, Beirut, 1965).
5. Briks, P. Djâmi Nabî Yunîs : Shrine of the Prophet Jonah in Nineveh. in *Awîlum ša la mašê - man who cannot be forgotten : Studies in Honor of Prof. Stefan Zawadzki Presented on the Occasion of his 70th Birthday* (eds. Koliński, R., Prostko-Prostyński, J. & Tyborowski, W.) 1–19 (Ugarit Verlag, Muenster, 2018).
6. Nováček, K., Melčák, M., Beránek, O. & Starková, L. *Mosul after Islamic State. The Quest for Lost Architectural Heritage. With Contribution of Lucie Pospíšilová*. (Palgrave Macmillan, Cham, Switzerland, 2021).
7. Niebuhr, C. *Reisebeschreibung nach Arabien und anderen umliegenden Laendern. Zweiter Band*. (Hofdruckerei bei Nicolaus Moeller, Kopenhagen, 1778).
8. Coupperie, M. P.-A. Mission de Babylone. in *Annales de l'Association de la Propagation de la Foi. Recueil Périodique des Lettres des Évêques et des Missionnaires des Missions des Deux Mondes, et de Tous les Documents Relatifs aux Missions et à l'Association de la Propagation de la Foi. No XIX* vol. 19 (P. Rusand, Imprimeur-Libraire; Librairie Ecclésiastique, Lyon; Paris, 1830).
9. Rich, C. J. *Narrative of a Residence in Koordistan, and of Ancient Nineveh; with Journal of a Voyage Down the Tigris to Bagdad and an Account of a Visit to Shirauz and Persepolis. Vol. II*. vol. 2 (James Duncan, London, 1836).
10. Sarre, F. & Herzfeld, E. *Archäologische Reise im Euphrat- und Tigris-Gebiet. In vier Bänden. Band II. Mit einem Beitrage: Rušāfah von Samuel Guyer. Mit 245 Textabbildungen und 2 Karten*. vol. 2 (Dietrich Reimer / Ernst Vohsen / A.-G., Berlin, 1920).
11. Streck, M. Nīnawā. *Enzyklopaedie des Islam. Geographisches, Ethnographisches und Biographisches Wörterbuch der Muhammedanischen Völker. Ergänzungsband 182–186* (1938).
12. Al-Muqaddasi, Ranking, G. S. A. & Azoo, R. F. *Aḥsanu-t-Taqāsīm Fī Ma'rifati-l-Aqālīm Known as Al-Muqaddasī. Translated from Arabic and Edited by Surgeon-Lt.Col. G. S. A. Ranking, M.D., M.R.A.S.* (Asiatic Society of Bengal, Kolkata, 1897).
13. Al-Harawi & Sourdél-Thomine, J. *Abū'l-Hassan 'Alī B. Abī Bakr Al-Harawī mort à Alep en 611/1215. Guide des Lieux de Pèlerinage. Traduction annotée par Janine Sourdél-Thomine*. (Institut Français de Damas, Damascus, 1957).

14. Ibn Jubayr & Wright, W. *The Travels of Ibn Jubayr. Edited from a MS. in the University Library of Leyden by William Wright. Second Edition Revised by M. J. de Goeje and Printed for the Trustees of the 'E. J. W. Gibb Memorial'*. (E. J. Brill, Imprimerie Orientale; Luzac & Co., Leiden; London, 1907).
15. *The Holy Bible from the Ancient Eastern Text: George M. Lamsa's Translations from the Aramaic of the Peshitta*. (Harper & Row, San Francisco, 1985).
16. Aguilar, J. Recovering deliberately destroyed cultural heritage. in *Mémoires futures / Zukünftige Erinnerungen. Le patrimoine culturel au Luxembourg / Kulturerbe in Luxemburg* (eds. Schleich, N. & Commission luxembourgeoise pour l'UNESCO) 134–143 (Commission luxembourgeoise pour l'UNESCO, Luxembourg, 2025).
17. Kashima, Y. How can you capture cultural dynamics? *Frontiers in Psychology* **5**, (2014).
18. Kennedy, M. Mosul: Iraqi troops find Assyrian treasures in network of Isis tunnels. *The Guardian* (2017).
19. Majeed, H. Tunnels under ancient Mosul mosque show Islamic State's focus on loot. *Reuters* (2017).
20. Layard, A. H. *Discoveries among the Ruins of Nineveh and Babylon; with Travels in Armenia, Kurdistan, and the Desert: Being the Result of a Second Expedition Undertaken for the Trustees of the British Museum. Abridged from the Larger Work*. (G. P. Putnam & Co., New York, 1853).
21. Turner, G. Tell Nebi Yūnus: The ekal māšarti of Nineveh. *Iraq* **32**, 68–85 (1970).
22. Kertai, D. *The Architecture of Late Assyrian Royal Palaces*. (Oxford University Press, Oxford, 2015).
23. Reade, J. The Assyrian Palace at Nabi Yunus, Nineveh. in *At the Dawn of History. Ancient Near Eastern Studies in Honour of J.N. Postgate. Volume 2* (eds. Heffron, Y., Stone, A. & Worthington, M.) vol. 2 431–458 (Eisenbrauns, Winona Lake, Indiana, 2017).
24. Sennacherib, Grayson, A. K. & Novotny, J. R. *The Royal Inscriptions of Sennacherib, King of Assyria (704-681 BC), Part 1*. vol. 3/1 (Eisenbrauns, Winona Lake, Indiana, 2012).
25. Esarhaddon & Leichty, E. *The Royal Inscriptions of Esarhaddon, King of Assyria (680-669 BC)*. (Eisenbrauns, Winona Lake, Indiana, 2011).
26. Van de Mierop, M. The Sack of Nineveh in 612 BC. in *Nineveh: The Great City. Symbol of Beauty and Power* (eds. Petit, L. P. & Morandi Bonacossi, D.) 243–247 (Sidestone Press, Leiden, 2017).
27. Miglus, P. A. & Maul, S. M. Ninive. Verwüstung und Plünderung des letzten unerforschten assyrischen Königspalastes. in *Kulturraub - Fallbeispiele aus Syrien, Irak, Jemen, Ägypten und Libyen* (eds. Hemeier, B. & Sabrine, I.) 186–190 (Dietrich Reimer Verlag GmbH, Berlin, 2021).
28. Maul, S. M. *et al.* Erforschung des ekal māšarti auf Tell Nebi Yunus in Ninive 2018-2019. in *Zeitschrift für Orient-Archäologie* (Gebr. Mann Verlag, Berlin, 2021).

29. Kinzel, M. Take a look, make a sketch and re-think it: Surveying and 4D models for reconstructing archaeological sites. in *ARCHAIA - Case Studies on Research Planning, Characterisation, Conservation and Management of Archaeological Sites* (eds. Marchetti, N. & Thuesen, I.) 91–101 (Archaeopress Publishing Ltd., Oxford, 2008).
30. Xenophon, Ambler, W. & Buzzetti, E. *The Anabasis of Cyrus*. (Cornell University Press, Ithaca, New York, 2011).